

Spatio-Temporal Study of Changing Population Size from The Year 1991 To 2011: A Case Study of Karad Tehsil

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Abstract

The term population size indicates the total number of peoples in a particular land area during a specific time. Population size is a fundamental parameter of demographic study. Population census is a best source to collect the data of population size. Understands the changing behavior of the population based on population size. The changing population size controls to the pattern of population distribution. In the case of population size India is a second highest country in the world after China. The present research paper focuses on the spatio-temporal study of changing population size from the year 1991 to 2011. Karad is a geographically, Socio-economically and historically bounteous tehsil of Satara district and due to that cause highest population size is found in this tehsil as compare to other tehsils of Satara district. There are number of reasons behind the largest population size in the Karad tehsil such as good irrigation and transportation facilities, Education, banking and health facilities, number of opportunities in business and jobs etc.

Keywords: Population, Socio- Economic, Change, Education

Introduction

Here has been done a comparative study of population size and its spatial distribution in Karad tehsil from the year 1991 to 2011. There are used village wise population size of Karad tehsil of the decades 1990, 2000 and 2010. These data joined to village boundary map in Arc GIS. Interpolation method used to spatial distribution analysis. There are numbers of indicators which indicate the changing trend of population i.e. Population size and distribution, population growth, population density, sex composition and urbanization etc. According to the census 2011 the population size of India stood at 1,210,193,422 persons. Maharashtra state is India's second highest state in population size with 112,374,333 person's population size after Uttar Pradesh then Thane is highest district of Maharashtra population size with 11,060,148 persons. Satara district is there which hold 2.67 percent population of Maharashtra. Population size of Satara district is 3,003,741 persons.

Objectives

The main aim of the present research paper is to the spatio-temporal study of changing population size of Karad tehsil from the year 1991 to 2011.

Database and Methodology

The present research is based on the primary as well as secondary data base. These data again divides in to two groups those are spatial data and nonspatial data conducted with a geographical

Primary Data

Spatial Data:

- GPS Locations points for georeferencing and ground truths
- Geotagged Photos

Non-spatial Data

- Population counts through village survey
- Numerical and descriptive data through different

Primary Data

Spatial Data:

- Village boundary map and vector data set Geotagged Photos
- Toposheet
- Satellite Imageries

Non-spatial Data

- Censes Data
- District level socio-economic survey report
- Vital Statistics

Methodology

Fig. 1 Research Methodology

Research methodology is a pre constructed systematic design of the actual research. In the present research work concentrated on the study of population changing trend in Karad tehsil in the case of population density using temporal data. Different spatial analysis carried out in this research. For that analysis used different primary and secondary data in spatial and non-spatial modes which collected from different sources. In the process of analysis of this data appropriate different statistical techniques like percentage, average, growth, growth rates, variations, ratios etc.

Study Area

The main aim of present research to the spatio-temporal study of changing population size from the year 1991 to 2011 population density of Karad tehsil. The geographical extend of Karad tehsil is $17^{\circ}31'59.082''\text{N}$ to $17^{\circ}5'29.779''\text{N}$ latitude and $73^{\circ}58'59.705''\text{E}$ to $17^{\circ}18'58.985''\text{N}$ longitude. The elevation of Karad tehsil is ranging from minimum 552 mt.to maximum 920 mt. from mean sea level.

Fig. 2: Location Map of study Area

Data Analysis

Karad is a geographically, socio-economically and historically bounteous tehsil of Satara district and due to that cause highest population size is found in this tehsil as compare to other tehsils of Satara district. There are number of reasons behind the largest population size in the Karad tehsil such as good irrigation and transportation facilities, Education, banking and health facilities, number of opportunities in business and jobs etc.

Table:1: Population Size of Karad Tehsil

Year	Population			Decade Variation in %		
	Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban
1991	459955	403136	56819	-	-	-
2001	543424	483321	60103	18.15	19.89	5.78
2011	584085	454829	129256	7.48	-5.90	115.06

(Source – Census of India)

Table 3.3 shows the decade wise population size of Karad tehsil from the year 1991 to 2011 and these values graphically represents in chart 3.1. According to this table the population size of Karad tehsil is continuously growing from the years 1991 to 2011. In the decade 1990 the total population of Karad tehsil was 459955 and it grow by 83,459 and reached on 5,43,424 in the year 2001. In the decade of 2010, population size of the tehsil was grow by 40,661 and reached on 5,84,085. The statistics of decadal variation says that the population size of the tehsil is continuously growing from the years 1991 to 2011 but its growing rate is decreasing in same decades. The decade variation of total population size between the years 1991 and 2001 was 18.15% then this decade variation declined by 11.03% and reached on 7.48%.

In the case of rural-urban population size there is found an adverse satiation. In the year 1991, the rural population size of the tehsil was 403136 and it grow by 80185 and reached on 483321 in the year 2001. In the decade of 2010, rural population size of the tehsil was negatively grown. In this decade rural population size was decline by 28492 and reached on 454829 persons. There are abnormal changes found in the decadal variation of rural urban population size. The decade variation in the rural population size between the years 1991 and 2001 was 19.89% ad it declined by 24.98% and reached on -05.09% in the year 2001. The decadal variation of the urban population size was 5.78% in the year 2001 and it grow by 109.28% and it reached on 115.06% in the year 2011.

Fig. 3. Population Size of Karad Tehsil from 1991 to 2011

Fig 3.1 shows the spatial changing trend of the distribution of population size of Karad tehsil from the years 1991 to 2011. The present figure clearly shows that the population size of the tehsil is increasing decade to decade. But fifteen villages are there who shows revers proportion of population size as compare to another village's i.e. Kale, Karave, Pawarwadi, Atake, Narayanwadi, Yevati, Vanarwadi, Jinti, Bharewadi, Savade, Gamewadi, Shelakewadi, Kapil, Akaichiwadi and Pachund. These all villages located to southern side of the

tehsil excluding Gamewadi. Kale and Karve villages are there whose populationsize is rapidly declining from the year 1991 to 2011.

Fig. 4: Spatial Distribution of Population Size of Karad Tehsil:1991, 2001 and 2011
(Source – Census of India)

Results and Discussion

In the present research work analyzed necessary demographic data and find some results which discussed below.

1. The total population size of Karad tehsil is increasing from the year 1991 to 2011 but its growing rate is declining from decade to decade.
2. Rural population size of the tehsil was negatively grown in the year 2011 then urban population abnormally grew in this same year.
3. In the study area Kale and Karve villages are whose population size is rapidly and continuously declining from the year 1991 to 2011. This situation is generated due to unfavorable physical and socio-economic environment such as hilly terrain, lack of water sources, monsoon-based agriculture etc. And so, rural to urban migration effect shows in this situation.

Finally, we can conclude that the population size of Karad tehsil is not equally distributed. There are some socio-economic and Geophysical factors strongly affected on this population size.

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